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Models for Scheduling Batch Production of Items with Lot Streaming in Hybrid Flow Shops

Madalin-Gabriel CATANA

University POLITEHNICA of Bucharest, Manufacturing Engineering Department, Bucharest, Romania, mg_catana@yahoo.com

Abstract

Being a common concern faced by nowadays production managers, the problem of minimizing the makespan of batch production schedules of items by using the lot streaming strategy in hybrid flow shops is insufficiently studied by operations researchers. To address to the limitations found in the literature on this subject, this paper formulates two comprehensive mathematical models to solve the problem, a linear programming model and an enumeration model. The following general production conditions are supposed to exist by the models: a processing cycle time limit prescribed for the batch production of item; no-idling of batch operations; not-negligible times for transportation of streamed lots between processing stages; a multi-machine or a single-machine processing of lots at the parallel machine group in each stage; not-negligible times for set-up the stage operations; an anticipative or a reactive scheduling of the setup work; a fixed number of equal-size lots used for streaming the batch production. Under these conditions, the models minimize the length of batch production schedule by minimizing the start time lag between pairs of successive process operations. OpenSolver add-in for Microsoft Office Excel was used for implementing the linear programming model, and a Visual Basic for Applications procedure was coded in Excel for the enumeration model. A numerical example for the utilization of the models was used to discuss the quality of scheduling solutions under different models' settings, and also to compare in terms of quality and feasibility the solutions implying equal-size lots with other possible scheduling solutions, assuming optimally-sized, different-in-size lots.

Keywords: operations research, lot streaming, hybrid flow shop, scheduling, linear programming, spreadsheet optimization.

Introduction

A review of scientific literature concerning managerial solutions possible to be applied for reducing the makespan of batch production schedules of items is presented in the followings. Conclusions of the review are used to define after that motivation and scope of the study presented in this paper.

Literature Review

In the book by Catana (2019) is mentioned that batch production is the most prevalent manufacturing strategy that is employed in industry for an efficient fabrication of items. A batch for an item to be produced represents the quantity or the number of units of item that will be processed continuously in the shop after the setup of machines allocated for processing operations. Catana (2019) also observed that the size of a batch of item may be optimally determined by using production cost minimization mathematical models or may be imposed by production managers based on important manufacturing restrictions, such as the size and the frequency of distribution orders for the produced item.

To reduce the duration or makespan of batch production schedule for an item with multi-operational or multi-stage processing at different machines, the strategy of lot streaming is frequently used in industrial practice and, therefore, studied by operations researchers. As defined by Defersha (2011), lot streaming is the technique of splitting the production batch of an item in smaller-sized lots with

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individual transportation among the processing machines of a multi-stage manufacturing system, denoted flow shop, so that different processing operations of the batch can be overlapped in time, in order to shorten the makespan of batch production schedule. A comprehensive review of traditional settings and terminology of a lot streaming operations research problem is presented by Chang and Chiu (2005), who evoked the following main concerns of a problem of this nature: single-item or multiple-item batch production; equal, consistent or variable size for lots of item to be transported among the processing stages; integer or non-integer sizes of streamed (transported) lots; no-idling or intermittent idling of batch processing operations of item; an anticipative or a reactive operation and machine setup for processing the item batch; transportation time dependent or not-dependent on the streamed lot size; cost-based or time-based performance measures to be minimized. Typical decision variables for a lot streaming problem are considered to be the number and size of streamed lots in each item batch and the processing sequence or schedule for these lots at the machines in flow shop. As observed by Defersha (2011), most researches of lot streaming problem assumes the production environment of a pure flow shop, having only one processing machine available in each operational stage. Significant research contributions on traditional lot streaming problem in pure flow shops are presented within the books of Baker and Trietsch (2019) and of Sarin and Jaiprakash (2007), where numerous mathematical models and algorithms for making lot streaming decisions in both single-item and multiple-item batch production situations are shown. Other contributions relating specific solution procedures for different settings of lot streaming problem in pure flow shops are presented also by Chen and Steiner (1998), by Huang (2010), by Kalir and Sarin (2001) and by Low, Hsu and Huang (2004). Finally, the work of Catana, Neagu and Tonoiu (2009) uses the restrictions of a lot streaming strategy with known, equal-size streamed lots and no-idling of batch operations within a resource-constrained scheduling model for multiple-item batch production projects. The model was implemented in a Microsoft Office Excel workbook, with specially designed cell ranges for initial data input, and cell formulas and Visual Basic for Applications (VBA) code modules for solution output.

An other possible strategy to reduce the makespan of production schedule in the case of single-item or multiple-item batch manufacturing is to allocate the multi-operational processes to a hybrid flow shop (HFS), which comprises more than one machine available for utilization in several bottleneck processing stages and, therefore, permits different processing operations of items to be overlapped or even shortened in time. However, as observed by Defersha (2011), the majority of researches about the problem of production scheduling in hybrid flow shops with makespan minimization objective does not take into account the application of lot streaming strategy. Important contributions relating specific solution procedures for different formulations of multiple-item hybrid flow shop scheduling problem, with makespan minimization objective and in the absence of the lot streaming strategy, are presented in the books of Emmons and Vairaktarakis (2013), of Lopez and Roubellat (2008) and of Pinedo (2016). Besides, all the above studies and also the works of Burtseva et al (2012), of Defersha (2011), of Liu (2008) and of Zhang, Liu and Linn (2003), which investigate the use of lot streaming strategy in hybrid flow shops, consider the number of parallel machines available for the production of items in each processing stage of hybrid flow shop to be known beforehand, as an initial data for the scheduling problem. In the book by Catana (2019), it is commented that if there exists an average cycle time limit C to be met by a batch production process of an item with m operations performed in a hybrid flow shop with m processing stages, then the number of parallel machines M_k that should be allocated in stage k ($k = 1, \dots, m$) for the execution of operation with unit processing time P_k must be sized with the following equation:

$$M_k = \left\lceil \frac{P_k}{C} \right\rceil \dots \dots \dots (1)$$

Mathematical symbol $\lceil \cdot \rceil$ used in equation (1) denotes the round-up to the smallest integer function.

An even higher degree of batch production makespan reduction can be obtained when employing the strategy of lot streaming for multi-operational processes run in hybrid flow shops, as demonstrated by the researches of Burtseva et al (2012), of Defersha (2011), of Liu (2008) and of Zhang, Liu and Linn (2003). All these researches propose mixed integer linear programming (MILP) formulations for the specific hybrid flow shop lot streaming problem taken into account. All the models are constructed

with the constraint that a streamed lot is to be allocated for processing on exactly one machine from those, several, available for utilization in a manufacturing stage of hybrid flow shop. This constraint corresponds to the application of a single-machine processing scheme (SP) for streamed lots at the manufacturing stages of hybrid flow shop. It will be demonstrated in this research that for streamed lots of large size, SP scheme becomes less effective in ensuring a high utilization level for the group of M_k parallel machines throughout the processing time of operation k , in order to meet the required process cycle time C . A different processing scheme for lots that will be investigated in this research is expected to improve the utilization level for the group of M_k parallel machines. This is the multi-machine processing scheme (MP) for streamed lots at the manufacturing stages of hybrid flow shop, implying the split of each lot in balanced shares to be processed in parallel by all the machines in the group. This scheme may easily be implemented in production by maintaining unique work-in-process input buffers in front of the groups of parallel machines available in processing stages of hybrid flow shop. Another constraint that is used in the MILP models of Liu (2008) and of Zhang, Liu and Linn (2003) concerns a so called “rotation” method to be applied for deciding the allocation of streamed lots to individual machines in a stage while using SP scheme. This method proved to be supportive for makespan minimization of single-item batch production schedules by allocating evenly the lots to machines in a group, as follows: lot 1 to machine 1; lot 2 to machine 2; ...; lot M_k to machine M_k ; lot $M_k + 1$ to machine 1 and so on. An adapted allocation method that will be used in this research for the case of MP scheme implies a unit-based allocation of item to machines, as follows: unit 1 in the batch to machine 1; unit 2 to machine 2; ...; unit M_k to machine M_k ; unit $M_k + 1$ to machine 1 and so on. As all the four researches mentioned before do consider a negligible transportation time of streamed lots between processing stages, this research will examine also the influence of the lot transportation time on the makespan of batch production schedule. Moreover, there will be studied the influence exerted on schedule makespan by each stage setup time required before processing the item batch, by taking into consideration two alternative setup schemes possible to be applied according to item’s process plan: the anticipative setup (AS), which can be started at the machines in a stage before the arrival of any streamed lot from the previous processing stage; reactive setup (RS), which can be started at the machines in a stage only after the arrival of required number of streamed lots coming from the earlier processing stage. The schedule for setup work in a stage will depend on both the adopted streamed lot processing scheme (SP or MP) and operation setup scheme (AS or RS), and on general requirements to achieve the continuity of entire batch operation (no-idling requirement) and to ensure the highest possible utilization level for machine group in the stage during the batch operation execution time. A direct consequence of the latter requirement is that all the parallel machines in a processing stage will have a common setup schedule, in order to be set-up for the stage operation in the same time interval.

Motivation and scope of present research

Literature review from above clearly indicates that the use of lot streaming strategy in a hybrid flow shop is the most effective option for reducing schedules makespan for single-item multi-operational batch production processes with cycle time limits that must be met. However, the review concludes also that the research contributions on lot streaming batch production in hybrid flow shops should be much more numerous, diverse or complete, in order to effectively be applied in managerial practice.

Present research is primarily focused on the sequencing and scheduling components of lot streaming problem, in the case of a single-item multi-operational batch production process run in a multi-stage hybrid flow shop. The number of machines in each processing stage of hybrid flow shop is sized in accordance with the cycle time limit prescribed for entire process. Research objective is to find the batch production schedule of shortest length, given by the combinations of SP and MP lot processing schemes with AS and RS operation setup schemes, under the restrictions of no-idling the operations and of best-using the operational time of parallel machines in hybrid flow shop. A “rotation” method adapted for streamed lot processing schemes SP and MP is used for allocating the lots to individual machines in a group. Transportation time of streamed lots between processing stages and setup time of stage operations are taken into account in scheduling. The number of streamed lots in the batch is considered to be known in advance, as it could come from limited number of available transporters as mentioned by Kalir and Sarin (2001) or from the solution of a transportation cost minimization model as indicated by Catana (2019). The streamed lots are considered to be integers of equal size for easy

management, but solutions of the problem with different, optimized integer sizes of lots will be also provided and compared in terms of quality and feasibility with equal-size lot scheduling solutions.

To address to the issues mentioned above, two models for scheduling batch production of items with lot streaming in hybrid flow shops, a linear programming (LP) model and an enumeration model, are proposed in section 2 of this paper. Implementation of the proposed models in Microsoft Office Excel spreadsheet formats, by means of OpenSolver optimization add-in by Mason (2012) and VBA code, is then presented in section 3. A numerical example for the utilization of the models is provided after that in section 4, and comparisons are made on the quality and feasibility of solutions under different models' settings. Research conclusions are displayed in section 5 of the paper.

Models for scheduling of batch production with lot streaming in HFS

For describing the two mathematical models proposed for scheduling the batch production with lot streaming in HFS, it is necessary to previously define the underlying problem parameters as shown below. These parameters will be subsequently used in the formulation of the models.

Definition of Problem Parameters

Let be:

- m Number of processing stages in HFS where stages are indexed by k with $k = 1, \dots, m$;
- P_k Processing time for one unit of item in the operation performed in stage k ;
- C Average processing cycle time limit to be met in each batch production operation of item;
- U_k Setup time for operation on each machine available for batch processing in stage k ;
- T_k Transportation time for each lot streamed from processing stage k to the following stage;
- M_k Number of parallel machines required to be set-up and used for item batch processing in stage k of HFS, which comes from equation (1);
- B Size of processing batch of the item in each operation performed in HFS;
- n Number of streamed lots in the batch where lots are indexed by i with $i = 1, \dots, n$;
- L Size of each streamed lot throughout the process run in HFS, which is given by equation:

$$L = \frac{B}{n} \dots\dots\dots(2)$$

- b_{SP} Binary data equal to 1 if SP scheme will be used for scheduling the processing of streamed lots at parallel machines allocated to operations, and equal to 0 otherwise;
- b_{MP} Binary data equal to 1 if MP scheme will be used for scheduling the processing of streamed lots at parallel machines allocated to operations, and equal to 0 otherwise;
- b_{AS} Binary data equal to 1 if AS scheme will be used for scheduling the setup time of parallel machines allocated to operations, and equal to 0 otherwise;
- b_{RS} Binary data equal to 1 if RS scheme will be used for scheduling the setup time of parallel machines allocated to operations, and equal to 0 otherwise;
- $S_{k,i}$ Start time of the part of operation in stage k related to the process of streamed lot i , which is expressed relative to the beginning of operation setup with general equation:

$$S_{k,i} = b_{MP} \cdot (P_k \cdot \lfloor L \cdot (i-1) / M_k \rfloor + X_{k,i}) + b_{SP} \cdot (P_k \cdot L \cdot \lfloor (i-1) / M_k \rfloor + Y_{k,i}) \dots\dots\dots(3)$$

In equation (3), mathematical symbol $\lfloor \cdot \rfloor$ stands for the round-down to the largest integer function and terms $X_{k,i}$ and $Y_{k,i}$ control the inclusion of setup time in value $S_{k,i}$ as follows:

$$X_{k,i} = \begin{cases} 0, & \text{if } \lfloor L \cdot (i-1) / M_k \rfloor = 0 \\ U_k, & \text{if } \lfloor L \cdot (i-1) / M_k \rfloor > 0 \end{cases} \dots\dots\dots(4)$$

$$Y_{k,i} = \begin{cases} 0, & \text{if } \lfloor (i-1) / M_k \rfloor = 0 \\ U_k, & \text{if } \lfloor (i-1) / M_k \rfloor > 0 \end{cases} \dots\dots\dots(5)$$

- $F_{k,i}$ Finish time of the part of operation in stage k related to the process of streamed lot i , which is expressed relative to the beginning of operation setup with general equation:

$$F_{k,i} = b_{MP} \cdot (P_k \cdot \lceil L \cdot i / M_k \rceil + U_k) + b_{SP} \cdot (P_k \cdot L \cdot \lceil i / M_k \rceil + U_k) \dots\dots\dots(6)$$

$S_{k+I,k}$ Start time lag of successive operations k and $k+I$ with respect to the item batch, which is the minimum positive distance in time that may exist between the starts of operations k and $k+I$ under all the constraints of scheduling models (this parameter will be optimized by models);

$T_{k+I,k,i}$ Transfer time lag of successive operations k and $k+I$ with respect to the streamed lot i in the batch is deduced with the following equation and should suit the required transportation time of lot i between operational stages:

$$T_{k+I,k,i} = S_{k+I,k} + S_{k+I,i} - F_{k,i} \dots\dots\dots(7)$$

D_k Duration of batch operation in stage k is dependent on the processing scheme of streamed lots and may be obtained with the following general equation in case of equal-size lots:

$$D_k = b_{MP} \cdot (P_k \cdot \lceil B / M_k \rceil + U_k) + b_{SP} \cdot (P_k \cdot L \cdot \lceil n / M_k \rceil + U_k) \dots\dots\dots(8)$$

In general, D_k is the distance in time between the start and the finish of operation in stage k ;

D Duration (makespan) of the schedule of batch production process is given by the equation:

$$D = \sum_{k=1}^{m-1} S_{k+I,k} + D_m \dots\dots\dots(9)$$

In general, D is the distance in time between the start of first batch operation (in stage 1) and the finish of the last batch operation (in stage m).

It is worthy to be pointed out that all terms in equations (3) and (6) besides $X_{k,i}$, $Y_{k,i}$ and U_k define the limits of scheduling interval for processing the lot i in operation k , under the conditions of no-idling the batch operation and of the specific “rotation” method used for scheduling the processing time of equal-sized lots within MP and SP schemes.

Definition of Linear Programming Model

By using the parameters introduced above, the linear program for scheduling the batch production of an item with lot streaming in HFS is described below. The objective function and the constraints of LP model concern the part of production schedule relating to a pair of generic, successive operations k and $k+I$.

Minimize $S_{k+I,k} \dots\dots\dots(10)$

Subject to:

$$S_{k+I,k} \geq 0 \dots\dots\dots(11)$$

$$T_{k+I,k,i} \geq b_{MP} \cdot (b_{AS} \cdot (T_k - U_{k+I} + X_{k+I,i}) + b_{RS} \cdot T_k) + b_{SP} \cdot (b_{AS} \cdot (T_k - U_{k+I} + Y_{k+I,i}) + b_{RS} \cdot T_k) \dots\dots(12)$$

$\forall(i = 1, \dots, n)$.

The objective function in equation (10) is to minimize the start time lag of successive operations k and $k+I$, which is equivalent to minimizing the schedule makespan for batch production process, in the conditions of equations (8) and (9). The constraint in equation (11) ensures the condition of non-negativity for the model variable and objective function $S_{k+I,k}$. The group of constraints in equation (12) provides that the transfer time lag of successive operations k and $k+I$ for each streamed lot i is larger than or equal with a minimum value required to accommodate the transportation time of lot under different combinations of schemes applied for lot processing and operation setup. It is evident that despite the comprehensiveness of this model accompanied by the data given by equations (1) to (7), to solve the model one should use proper binary values for the parameters b_{SP} , b_{MP} , b_{AS} and b_{RS} according to the schemes chosen for lot processing and operation setup.

Definition of Enumeration Model

The enumeration model designed for scheduling the batch production of an item with lot streaming in HFS is based on the algorithm shown in pseudocode below. The approach of the model is to calculate repetitively, for each operation k with $k = 1, \dots, m-1$ and each lot i with $i = 1, \dots, n$, the minimum start time lag $S_{k+I,k,i}$ required to exist among operations k and $k+I$ under the constraints of needed transfer

of lot i between operational stages and of applied schemes for operation setup and lot processing. The largest value of $S_{k+1,k,i}$ for all lots streamed from operation k is retained as the start time lag $S_{k+1,k}$ and it is used afterwards to compute start and finish times S_k and F_k for each operation k with $k = 1, \dots, m$. Specific equations that are used in the model for the calculation of parameter $S_{k+1,k,i}$ are as follows:

$S_{k+1,k,i}$ For the combination of MP and AS schemes:

$$S_{k+1,k,i} = U_k + P_k \cdot \lceil L \cdot i / M_k \rceil + T_k - U_{k+1} - P_{k+1} \cdot \lfloor L \cdot (i-1) / M_{k+1} \rfloor \dots\dots\dots(13)$$

For the combination of MP and RS schemes:

$$S_{k+1,k,i} = U_k + P_k \cdot \lceil L \cdot i / M_k \rceil + T_k - X_{k+1,i} - P_{k+1} \cdot \lfloor L \cdot (i-1) / M_{k+1} \rfloor \dots\dots\dots(14)$$

with term $X_{k+1,i}$ obtained with equation (4);

For the combination of SP and AS schemes:

$$S_{k+1,k,i} = U_k + P_k \cdot L \cdot \lceil i / M_k \rceil + T_k - U_{k+1} - P_{k+1} \cdot L \cdot \lfloor (i-1) / M_{k+1} \rfloor \dots\dots\dots(15)$$

For the combination of SP and RS schemes:

$$S_{k+1,k,i} = U_k + P_k \cdot L \cdot \lceil i / M_k \rceil + T_k - Y_{k+1,i} - P_{k+1} \cdot L \cdot \lfloor (i-1) / M_{k+1} \rfloor \dots\dots\dots(16)$$

with term $Y_{k+1,i}$ obtained with equation (5).

The algorithm for enumeration model is as follows.

```

Read initial data:  $m, C, B, n, L; P_k, U_k, T_k, M_k$  for each  $k; D_k$  for each  $k$  and scheme MP and SP
For  $k = 1$  To  $m - 1$ 
  Let  $S_{k+1,k} = 0$  for each of AS and RS schemes
  For  $i = 1$  To  $n$ 
    Calculate  $S_{k+1,k,i}$  with equation (13) for the combination of MP and AS schemes
    Calculate  $S_{k+1,k,i}$  with equation (14) for the combination of MP and RS schemes
    Let  $S_{k+1,k} = \max(S_{k+1,k}, S_{k+1,k,i})$  for each of AS and RS schemes
  Next  $i$ 
Next  $k$ 
For  $k = 1$  To  $m - 1$ 
  Let  $S_{k+1,k} = 0$  for each of AS and RS schemes
  For  $i = 1$  To  $n$ 
    Calculate  $S_{k+1,k,i}$  with equation (15) for the combination of SP and AS schemes
    Calculate  $S_{k+1,k,i}$  with equation (16) for the combination of SP and RS schemes
    Let  $S_{k+1,k} = \max(S_{k+1,k}, S_{k+1,k,i})$  for each of AS and RS schemes
  Next  $i$ 
Next  $k$ 
Let  $S_1 = 0, F_1 = D_1$  for the first operation in each of the four schedules given by combined schemes
For  $k = 2$  To  $m$ 
  Let  $S_k = S_{k-1} + S_{k,k-1}$  for each of the four schedules given by combined schemes
  Let  $F_k = S_k + D_k$  for each of the four schedules given by combined schemes
Next  $k$ 
Write solution data  $S_k$  and  $F_k$  for each operation  $k$  in the four schedules given by combined schemes
    
```

Spreadsheet implementation of Scheduling Models

For an easier testing and utilization of the proposed models by scheduling scholars and practitioners, both models were implemented in Microsoft Office Excel worksheets, with required solution tools embedded inside the sheets as shown below.

Implementation of Linear Programming Model

Linear programming model and initial data required to be used by the model were arranged inside an Microsoft Office Excel worksheet as displayed in figure 1. The range of cells with green background in figure 1 contains manually-entered or formula-based calculated initial data. Data within this region

is used by the formulas provided in the range of cells with yellow background, where the LP model is located. Only the binary data indicating the alternative use of AS or RS and MP or SP schemes in the model is required to be manually-entered in the yellow part of the sheet. As OpenSolver optimization add-in for Microsoft Office Excel was used to declare the structure of the model (objective function, variables and constraints), this structure is indicated by highlighting and labeling the included cells as shown in figure 1. This feature and many other advantages of OpenSolver over Excel built-in Solver that were shown by Mason (2012) made that this add-in to be preferred for the implementation of LP model. As seen in figure 1, the implemented LP model locates in cell L7 the objective function and single decision variable described in equation (10), in range L7:M7 resides the constraint in equation (11) and in range J7:K11 are placed the constraints in equation (12). Optimal solution to the model is given by OpenSolver with the incorporated Coin-OR CBC linear optimization engine.

	A	B	C	D	E	F	G	H	I	J	K	L	M	N
1	Sch	Pk	Pk+1	C	Uk	Uk+1	Tk	Mk	Mk+1	B	L	n	Dk	Dk+1
2	MP	3.00	5.00	2.00	20.00	30.00	10.00	2	3	25	5	5	59.00	75.00
3	SP	3.00	5.00	2.00	20.00	30.00	10.00	2	3	25	5	5	65.00	80.00
4														
5	Linear programming model for scheduling with OpenSolver for Excel													
6	i	AS	RS	MP	SP	Sk,i	Fk,i	Sk+1,k + Sk+1,i	Sk+1,k + Fk+1,i	Tk+1,k,i	Tk+1,k,i >=	Sk+1,k=?	Sk+1,k >=	
7	1	1	0	1	0	0.00	29.00	10.00	50.00	-19.00	-20.00	10	>=	0
8	2					26.00	35.00	45.00	60.00	10.00	10.00			
9	3					35.00	44.00	55.00	65.00	11.00	>=	10.00		
10	4					41.00	50.00	65.00	75.00	15.00	10.00			
11	5					50.00	59.00	70.00	85.00	11.00	10.00			

Fig. 1: Excel worksheet with data of LP model

Implementation of Enumeration Model

A similar arrangement of model’s data in a Microsoft Office Excel worksheet was preferred also in the case of enumeration model, as observed in figure 2. The green range of cells in figure 2 contains manually-entered or formula-based calculated initial data, while the yellow range of cells holds the solution given by the VBA procedure attached to the brown command button with label “Schedule”. After initial data is entered and button “Schedule” is clicked, model solution will be written within the dedicated cells. The algorithm for enumeration model shown in previous section was translated into VBA code, as can be remarked in the portion of the code window displayed in figure 3. Slight difference may be observed between the names of some parameters in VBA code and in description of the model from previous section.

	A	B	C	D	E	F	G	H	I	J	K	L	M	N	O	P	Q	R	S	T
1	k	C	Pk	Uk	Tk	B	n	Mk	Dk,MP	Dk,SP	Schedule	SK,AS+MP	FK,AS+MP	SK,RS+MP	FK,RS+MP	SK,AS+SP	FK,AS+SP	SK,RS+SP	FK,RS+SP	
2	1	2.00	3.00	20.00	10.00	25	5	2	59.00	65.00		0.00	59.00	0.00	59.00	0.00	65.00	0.00	65.00	
3	2	2.00	5.00	30.00	10.00	25	5	3	75.00	80.00		10.00	85.00	39.00	114.00	30.00	110.00	60.00	140.00	

Fig. 2: Excel worksheet with data of enumeration model

```

CommandButton1_Click()
Private Sub CommandButton1_Click()
'VBA procedure for scheduling single-item batch production operations under lot streaming in multi-stage HFS,
'with anticipative/reactive setup of operations (AS/RS) and multi-machine/single-machine processing of streamed lots (MP/SP)
On Error GoTo Err
'Reading of initial data from Excel worksheet
n = WorksheetFunction.Max(Range(Cells(2, 1), Cells(1002, 1)))
ReDim Fk(1 To m), Uk(1 To m), Tk(1 To m), Mk(1 To m), DkMP(1 To m), DkSP(1 To m)
ReDim SkkASMP(1 To m - 1), SkkRSMP(1 To m - 1), SkkASSP(1 To m - 1), SkkRSSP(1 To m - 1)
ReDim SkASMP(1 To m), FkASMP(1 To m), SkRSMP(1 To m), FkRSMP(1 To m)
ReDim SkASSP(1 To m), FkASSP(1 To m), SkRSSP(1 To m), FkRSSP(1 To m)
B = Cells(2, 6).Value
n = Cells(2, 7).Value
L = B / n
For k = 1 To m
Fk(k) = Cells(1 + k, 3).Value
Uk(k) = Cells(1 + k, 4).Value
Tk(k) = Cells(1 + k, 5).Value
Mk(k) = Cells(1 + k, 8).Value
DkMP(k) = Cells(1 + k, 9).Value
DkSP(k) = Cells(1 + k, 10).Value
Next k
'Calculation of the minimum start time lags for operations on process batch in the case that MP scheme is applied
For k = 1 To m - 1
SkkASMP(k) = 0
SkkRSMP(k) = 0
For i = 1 To n
SkkASi = Uk(k) + Fk(k) * WorksheetFunction.RoundUp(L * i / Mk(k), 0) + Tk(k) - Uk(k + 1) - Fk(k + 1) * WorksheetFunction.Rou
Select Case WorksheetFunction.RoundDown(L * (i - 1) / Mk(k + 1), 0)
Case 0
SkkRSi = Uk(k) + Fk(k) * WorksheetFunction.RoundUp(L * i / Mk(k), 0) + Tk(k) - Fk(k + 1) * WorksheetFunction.RoundDown(L * (
Case Else
SkkRSi = Uk(k) + Fk(k) * WorksheetFunction.RoundUp(L * i / Mk(k), 0) + Tk(k) - Uk(k + 1) - Fk(k + 1) * WorksheetFunction.Rou
End Select
'Case that AS scheme is used
SkkASMP(k) = WorksheetFunction.Max(SkkASMP(k), SkkASi)
'Case that RS scheme is used
SkkRSMP(k) = WorksheetFunction.Max(SkkRSMP(k), SkkRSi)
Next i
Next k
Next k

```

Fig. 3: Portion of Excel VBA code window implementing the algorithm of enumeration model

Numerical Example

A numerical example for the utilization of proposed models is presented in the following, by using the initial data already displayed in figures 1 and 2 from previous section. It can be noticed that the example concerns a batch production process with two operations, performed in a hybrid flow shop with the number of machines in the two stages sized in accordance with an imposed limit for process cycle time C of 2 minutes/unit. All the other times taken as initial data are also expressed in minutes. To compare the quality of scheduling solutions with respect to the level of utilization ensured for the group of parallel machines allocated for each stage, the average processing cycle time of operations will be used. A small average processing cycle time of an operation corresponds to a high utilization level of allocated machines. Average processing cycle time C_k concerning the operation with index k will be calculated with the following equation:

$$C_k = \frac{D_k - U_k}{B} \dots\dots\dots(17)$$

The four schedules given by the models with the provided initial data are depicted in figures 4, 5, 6 and 7. It can be checked that in the case of schedules from figures 4 and 5 based on MP scheme, C_1 is 1.56 and C_2 is 1.8, while for the schedules in figures 6 and 7 based on SP scheme, C_1 is 1.8 and C_2 is 2. Despite that all values meet the process cycle limit of 2 minutes/unit, the solutions obtained with MP scheme prove generally to be of a higher quality than those given by SP scheme. The makespan of batch production schedule is shortened by the usage of MP scheme instead of SP scheme for lots processing and also by the application of AS scheme instead of RS scheme for setup of operations.

Fig. 4: Allocation and schedule of equal-size streamed lots at machines under MP and AS schemes

Fig. 5: Allocation and schedule of equal-size streamed lots at machines under MP and RS schemes

Fig. 6: Allocation and schedule of equal-size streamed lots at machines under SP and AS schemes

Fig. 7: Allocation and schedule of equal-size streamed lots at machines under SP and RS schemes

In order to know if and how much the makespan of batch production schedule can be shortened more by the relaxation of the restriction to use equal-size streamed lots, the LP model discussed within this paper was radically adapted and transformed into a MILP model with the following main features: for a known number of not-nil streamed lots in the batch, the integer sizes of lots are optimized in order to give the shortest possible makespan of production schedule and the highest quality of the schedule (measured by C_k values) under different combinations of MP or SP and AS or RS schemes. Solution shown in figure 8 relates the combination of MP and AS schemes, while that in figure 9 refers to the combination of SP and RS schemes. It can be remarked that the schedule makespan is shortened by the solution in figure 8 only with one minute as compared to the solution in figure 4 (with equal-size streamed lots). However, schedule in figure 9 is eleven minutes shorter than the equivalent schedule in figure 7 (with equal-size streamed lots). The roughly 2 percent reduction of production makespan in the first case may not worth the difficulties of monitoring the streaming of variable size lots, while the nearly 8 percent reduction in the second case may probably be worthy.

Fig. 8: Allocation and schedule of optimally-sized streamed lots at machines for MP and AS schemes

Fig. 9: Allocation and schedule of optimally-sized streamed lots at machines for SP and RS schemes

Conclusions

Present study was motivated by the observed limitations of the published researches in addressing to the scheduling issues related to the problem of streaming the batch production of items in multi-stage hybrid flow shops. There is made no connection in the relevant researches between the sizing of the processing stages of hybrid flow shops and the cycle time limits commonly prescribed for the batch production processes of items. Furthermore, existing researches on the optimization of lot streaming production in hybrid flow shops don't mention the multi-machine processing as a possible scheme to allocate the streamed lots to parallel machines in a processing stage, and also they do not investigate the combined influence exerted on the production schedule makespan by the transportation times and processing schemes adopted for streamed lots and by setup times and setup schemes that are used for operations. Under these circumstances, this paper proposes two comprehensive mathematical models, a linear programming model and an enumeration model, that can be used for optimal scheduling the batch production of an item in the case of lot streaming in a hybrid flow shop, under the most general production conditions. A fixed number of streamed lots and an equal size of lots are considered in the models. Proposed models were implemented in Microsoft Office Excel worksheets and were solved to optimality with OpenSolver optimization add-in, in the case of first model, and with a VBA coded procedure, in the case of second model. A numerical example for the utilization of scheduling models was also presented, and obtained solutions were compared with respect to their quality. Two solutions of the lot streaming problem having optimally-sized, different-in-size lots were finally revealed and compared with equal-size lot solutions in terms of makespan length and of feasibility for application in practice. The models presented in this paper are flexible enough to be applied without modification for optimizing batch production schedules of items produced with lot streaming in pure flow shops or even without lot streaming in pure or hybrid shops.

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